

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

Munisa Eshmuminova

Sophomore student of UzSWLU

Research advisor: Yuldasheva F.F

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7422319>

Abstract. This article fully describes the methods of teaching English, the use of modern technologies in teaching English, the goals and tasks of teaching English, and the role of English in our society.

Key words: English language, teaching methods, innovative technologies, effectiveness.

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье полностью описаны методы обучения английскому языку, использование современных технологий в обучении английскому языку, цели и задачи обучения английскому языку, а также роль английского языка в нашем обществе.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, методика обучения, инновационные технологии, эффективность.

After our country gained independence, the interest of young people in learning foreign languages increased, and many opportunities for language learning were created in our country. As stated by the first President Islam Karimov: "Currently, in our country, great attention is paid to the teaching of foreign languages. This is certainly not in vain.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Currently, ensuring the quality of teaching foreign languages to the growing young generation, fundamentally improving the system of training specialists who can speak foreign languages fluently, training mature personnel who meet world educational standards by mastering foreign languages is being carried out in our country. One of the goals of education is reform. Identifying opportunities in language teaching and bringing them to life, the teacher's knowledge, creativity, the ability to arouse students' love for their subject, and the establishment of a cooperative relationship with students are the requirements of the current era. At the same time, it should be said that each language being studied has its own rules and secrets. In order to become a mature specialist who meets international standards, the learner is required not to overlook the subtlest layers of the language.

There is no need to overestimate the importance of learning foreign languages for our country, which is striving to take a worthy place in the world community, and for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation. with our foreign partners." Especially in primary education.

Recently, the number of people of all ages learning English is increasing. This is because it is becoming more and more difficult to live without knowing English throughout life. But language learning also depends on age. Scientists have even proven that children learn languages faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are children's natural tendency to learn languages, strong ability to imitate, children having more time than adults, and quickly retaining learned information in their memory.

Masaru Ibuka, one of the Chinese inventors, wrote in his famous book "After it's too late": "...a child's brain can store an infinite amount of information...". It should also be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, you should not start teaching English to elementary school students who are learning English with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the very first step of teaching a foreign language, it can tire the child and weaken his interest in learning the language. Because teaching a foreign language to elementary school students is difficult and at the same time one of the

responsible tasks. That is why the following innovative methods can be used to teach English language meaningfully and interestingly to elementary school students:

Remembering by sight young children are known to remember things they see better than what they hear. Therefore, teaching new words by writing on things that are seen and often used in everyday life and making sentences with the new words learned. For example, writing on a book, a table, a blackboard, a pen, a window... Since such things are often seen and used in everyday life, the child learns these words involuntarily.

Using songs and poems to sing words that are difficult to understand or remember. Along with remembering new words, the child's speech also develops. For example, children can be shown to learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing.

In fact, language learning through the senses is more useful and effective than other methods. For example, in the process of tasting a single apple, the student knows its color, taste, size, smell, and also says its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the children the English name of the colors, the children immediately remember the time when they ate the fruit. Therefore, the use of such methods helps the student to retain information in his memory for a long time.

In conclusion, teaching language to elementary school students is not a chore, but rather fun games and innovative methods can serve as a foundation for their future learning. Therefore, as the educational system also sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we, future teachers, will better develop ways to effectively use innovative technologies. we can contribute.

REFERENCES

1. Turdaliyeva G.N "Boshlang'ich sinflarda ingliz tilini o'qitishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsiyalar"// 2020.
2. Bekmuratova U.B "Ingliz tilini o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish" // Toshkent 2012.
3. Toliboboeva, S. J. (2020). TEACHING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH. ScienceandEducation, 1(Special Issue2).
4. 4.. Толибобоева, III. (2020). Ingliz tilini o'qitishdagi zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari. YoungScientist, 19(309), 581-582.
5. Juldashева, N. N. (2020). Хорижий тилларни уқитишда ахборот технологиялар ва инновацион методларнинг ўрни. Молодой ученый. (12), 332-333.